

Determinants of Price Fluctuation and Profitability along the Cowpea Value Chain in Sokoto Metropolis, Nigeria

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This study analyze factors that influences price fluctuation and to evaluate the cost and return of Cowpea Marketing in Sokoto Metropolis, Nigeria, with emphasis on evaluating factors influencing price fluctuation, and assessing cost and returns. Primary data were obtained from 100 cowpea marketers using a structured questionnaire and analyzed through descriptive statistics, multiple regression, and cost– return analysis. Findings revealed that 58% of respondents were within the active age range of 31–50 years, 64% were married, and 46% possessed secondary education, indicating that the trade is dominated by middle-aged, moderately educated individuals with family responsibilities. Regression results showed that seasonality, transportation cost, storage conditions, and market demand significantly ($p < 0.05$) influenced price fluctuations. Cost and return analysis revealed an average total cost of ₦836,200, a gross margin of ₦135,800, and a net return of ₦113,800, yielding a return on naira invested of ₦0.14, confirming that cowpea marketing is profitable though constrained by infrastructural and financial challenges. The study concludes that improving access to credit, enhancing market information systems, and upgrading storage and transport infrastructure would substantially improve marketing efficiency and profitability in Sokoto-Metropolis.

Keywords: Cowpea marketing; Price fluctuation; Cost and returns; Market efficiency; Credit.

INTRODUCTION

Cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata*) is one of the most important grain legumes in sub-Saharan Africa, particularly in Nigeria, where it serves as a major source of affordable protein, income, and employment for both rural and urban households. Nigeria is the largest producer and consumer of cowpea globally, contributing significantly to food security and agricultural livelihoods (FAO, 2022). In northern Nigeria, especially Sokoto State, cowpea plays a vital role in the agrarian economy due to its adaptability to semi-arid conditions and its importance in local diets and trade.

The cowpea value chain encompasses a wide range of activities, including production, aggregation, transportation, storage, processing, and marketing.

Efficient functioning of this value chain is crucial for ensuring stable prices, reducing post-harvest losses, and improving returns to market participants. However, in many developing economies, including Nigeria, agricultural value chains are often characterized by inefficiencies such as poor infrastructure, inadequate storage facilities, limited access to credit, and weak market information systems, all of which contribute to price instability (Adeoye et al., 2019).

In Sokoto State, cowpea marketing is a key economic activity, particularly within urban centers such as Sokoto metropolis, where traders play an essential role in linking producers to consumers. Despite its importance, the cowpea market is subject to significant price fluctuations driven by seasonal variations, transportation costs, storage constraints, and changing demand patterns. These fluctuations not only affect marketers' profitability but also influence consumer access and affordability. Seasonal scarcity during the off-harvest period often

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Figure 1. Map of the study Area

leads to price spikes, while glut during harvest seasons can result in price drops, thereby affecting income stability for market actors (Abdullahi & Mohammed, 2020).

Understanding the determinants of price fluctuation within the cowpea value chain is essential for designing appropriate interventions aimed at improving market performance. Additionally, evaluating the cost and return structure of cowpea marketing provides insight into its profitability and economic viability. Previous studies have highlighted that although cowpea marketing is generally profitable in Nigeria, its full potential is constrained by high transaction costs, inadequate infrastructure, and limited access to formal financing (Ogunleye et al., 2018). Given the strategic importance of cowpea in Sokoto State and Nigeria at large, there is a need for a comprehensive value chain analysis that integrates price dynamics with cost and return assessment. Such analysis will not only enhance understanding of the factors influencing price fluctuations but also provide evidence-based recommendations for improving marketing efficiency, profitability, and overall value chain performance.

METHODOLOGY

Study Area

The study was conducted in Sokoto State. The State is

one of the 36 States of the Federal Republic of Nigeria. It is made up of 23 Local Government Areas (LGAs). Sokoto State occupies the Northwestern position of the Six Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria (with Sokoto as its capital) and shares common borders with Zamfara, Katsina, and Kebbi. The global location of the State is between longitude 4°-7° east of the Greenwich meridian and also between latitude 12°-14° North of the equator. The State occupies an area of approximately 25,973 square kilometers and has a population of 3,702,676 (NPC, 2006) and predicted as 7,097,136 in 2025.

About 80% of this population engages in peasant farming. There are two marked seasons in the State, the dry season and the rainy (wet) seasons. The rainy season, though brief, typically occurs between late May or early June and ends by September while the dry season, which spans from October to May, is usually prolonged and influenced by the harmattan a dry and dusty wind that blows from the Sahara desert and drastically reduces humidity (Adamu et al, 2020)

Sampling Procedure and Sample Size

A multi-stage sampling technique was used for sample selection to select the respondents across various cowpea actors in the Study area. The first stage was the Purposive Selection of Study Area. Sokoto State was purposively selected due to its prominence in cowpea production and trade. Within the state; Tsohuwar kasuwa,

Shagon goro, Babbar kasuwa, Kasuwar Dan kure, Kara market, and Hoqon Idi Market were chosen based on the intensity of cowpea marketing activities. In Stage 2, Respondents were stratified into key categories involved in cowpea marketing: Cowpea farmers, market traders and Wholesalers/intermediaries. This classification ensured that all levels of market actors will be adequately represented and in Stage 3, random sampling was used to select respondents from the identified markets making it a total of 100 responses. A sample size of 100 was chosen because it's considered statistically acceptable and accurate.

Data Collection and Analysis

Primary data collected in Sokoto Metropolis were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistical methods such SCP indices, Multiple Linear Regression Analysis and Gross margin and Net return analysis.

Multiple linear regression analysis

The aim is to identify various factors (dependent and independent) that affect the price of Cowpea both in rural and urban market.

$$P_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_5 + \beta_6 X_6 + \beta_7 X_7 + \mu \quad (1)$$

Where;

P_i = Price of cowpea per unit (dependent variable), X_1 = Seasonality (Dummy: 1 if yes; 0 otherwise), X_2 = Transportation Cost (Naira), X_3 = Storage availability (Dummy: 1 if yes; 0 otherwise), X_4 = Weather (Dummy: 1 if yes; 0 otherwise), X_5 = Market demand index (Volume of cowpea sold), X_6 = Government Policy (Dummy: 1 if yes; 0 otherwise), X_7 = Pests/Diseases outbreak (Dummy: 1 if yes; 0 otherwise), β_0 = Intercept (price when all other factors are zero), μ = Error term.

Gross Margin (GM) Model

The Gross Margin model measures the profitability performance of cowpea marketers. It represents the difference between the total revenue earned and the total variable cost incurred during marketing operations. A higher gross margin indicates better financial performance and efficient cost management. It can be mathematically expressed as:

$$GM = TR - TVC \quad (2)$$

Where:

GM = Gross Margin (₦ per marketer or per kilogram), TR = Total Revenue from cowpea sales (₦), TVC = Total Variable Cost of marketing cowpea (₦)

Marketing Margin (MM) Model

The Marketing Margin model measures the price spread between the consumer's price (selling price) and the producer's price (purchase or supply price). It shows the proportion of the consumer price retained by marketers as a reward for their marketing services, thereby reflecting pricing performance and market competitiveness. This can be mathematically expressed as:

$$MM = [(SP - PP) / SP] \times 100 \quad (3)$$

Where:

MM = Marketing Margin (%), SP = Selling Price of cowpea (₦/kg), PP = Purchase or Supply Price of cowpea (₦/kg)

Marketing Efficiency (ME) Model

The Marketing Efficiency model evaluates how effectively marketing inputs and resources are utilized in generating value. It assesses the ratio of value added through marketing to the total marketing cost. A higher efficiency value suggests that marketers are effectively converting costs into returns. This can be mathematically represented as:

$$ME = (VA / TMC) \times 100 \quad (4)$$

or equivalently,

$$ME = [(SP - PP) / MC] \times 100 \quad (5)$$

Where:

ME = Marketing Efficiency (%), VA = Value Added = (Selling Price – Purchase Price), TMC or MC = Total Marketing Cost (₦),

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Socio-economic Characteristics of the Cowpea Marketers

Age distribution of the cowpea marketers

The age distribution of respondents reveals that the majority (41%) of cowpea marketers fall within the age bracket of 35–44 years, followed by 24% in the 25–34 years category, and 18% within the 45–54 years range. A smaller proportion (5%) is above 55 years, while 12% are below 25 years of age. The mean age of 37.6 years, with a standard deviation of 10.88, indicates that the typical cowpea marketer in the study area is a middle-aged adult actively involved in the marketing process. These findings are consistent with results from previous studies.

Table 1: Socio-economic Characteristics of the Cowpea Marketers

Age Group	Frequency	Percentage	Mean
15–24	12	12.0	37.63
25–34	24	24.0	
35–44	41	41.0	
45–54	18	18.0	
> 54	5	5.0	
Sex			
Male	95	95.0	
Female	5	5.0	
Marital Status			
Single	32	32.0	
Married	64	64.0	
Divorced/Widowed	3	3.0	
Educational Level			
Islamic Education	5	5.0	
Primary Education	8	8.0	
Secondary Education	68	68.0	
Tertiary Education	19	19.0	
Occupation			
Cowpea Trader	67	67.0	
Farmer	17	17.0	
Civil Servant	7	7.0	
Artisan	6	6.0	
Others	3	3.0	
Household Size			Mean
1–3	13	13.0	6.32
4–6	47	47.0	
7–9	30	30.0	
10 and above	10	10.0	
Years of experience			Mean
1–5	23	23.0	10.34
6–10	35	35.0	
11–15	26	26.0	
16–20	11	11.0	
Above 20	5	5.0	
Cooperative Membership			
Member	38	38.0	
Non-member	62	62.0	
Total	100	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2025

For instance, Ibrahim et al. (2018) reported that most cowpea traders in Bauchi State were between 30 and 45 years, describing them as active and productive participants in the market. Similarly, Ojo et al. (2019) found that the mean age of grain traders in Kaduna State was approximately 38 years, closely aligning with the present study.

Sex distribution of the cowpea marketers

The results presented in Table 2 show that cowpea

marketing in the study area is overwhelmingly dominated by men, with 95% of the respondents being male and only 5% female. This wide gender disparity indicates that the cowpea trade is a male-driven enterprise in the region.

This result aligns with the findings of Audu et al. (2019), who reported that 90% of cowpea traders in Adamawa State were male, attributing the dominance to cultural restrictions and capital constraints faced by women. Similarly, Ogunleye et al. (2020) observed that the majority of legume traders in southwestern Nigeria were

Table 2: Regression matrix between price fluctuation and influencing factors

Variables (Predictors)	Coefficients (β)	Std. Error	t-value
Constant	—	1.074	4.871
Seasonality	0.327	0.118	3.661
Transportation	0.291	0.121	3.192
Storage Conditions	0.176	0.113	2.190
Market Demand	0.208	0.107	2.565
Weather	0.151	0.095	2.061
Government Policy	0.132	0.091	1.802
Pests and Diseases	0.116	0.079	1.783
R Square = 0.375 Adjusted R Square = 0.331 F = 7.89			

Source: Field Survey, 2025

men, citing limited access to credit and mobility as barriers for women.

Marital status of the cowpea marketers

The results presented in Table 3 indicate that a greater proportion of the respondents (64%) were married, while 32% were single and only 3% were divorced or widowed. This distribution shows that most cowpea marketers in the study area are married individuals. These findings are consistent with previous studies on agricultural marketing in Nigeria. Tanko et al. (2020) reported that the majority of grain traders in Niger State were married, suggesting that marital stability contributes to traders' reliability and enterprise sustainability.

Educational level of the cowpea marketers

The results presented indicate that a majority of the respondents (68%) have attained secondary education, while 19% possess tertiary education, 8% completed primary education, and 5% have Islamic education. This pattern clearly shows that cowpea marketers in the study area are predominantly educated, with over four-fifths (87%) having received at least secondary education. The findings of this study align closely with those of Audu et al. (2020), who found that 70% of grain traders in Benue State had at least secondary education and attributed their efficiency to the ability to interpret market trends and record transactions.

Occupation of the cowpea marketers

The occupational distribution of respondents presented in Table 3 shows that the majority (67%) are primarily engaged in cowpea trading as their main occupation. This

is followed by 17% who identify as farmers, 7% as civil servants, 6% as artisans, and 3% engaged in other occupations such as transportation or brokerage. The data suggest that cowpea marketing constitutes a major source of livelihood for most respondents, rather than a part-time or supplementary activity. These findings are consistent with those of Olayemi et al. (2019), who reported that most grain marketers in southwestern Nigeria were full-time traders, emphasizing the importance of trading as a core occupation in rural and peri-urban economies. Audu and Aliyu (2021) also observed that dual occupation between farming and trading enhances income stability and enables farmers to better understand market dynamics, thus reducing post-harvest losses.

Household size of the Cowpea marketers

The results show that almost half of the respondents (47%) have household sizes ranging between 4 and 6 persons, while 30% maintain moderately large households of 7–9 persons. Smaller households of 1–3 persons make up 13% of the sample, and 10% of respondents have large households comprising 10 members or more. The mean household size of 6.32 persons suggests that most respondents belong to medium-sized families, a pattern that is typical of rural and semi-urban households in Nigeria. This result corroborates the findings of Ibrahim et al. (2019), who reported an average household size of six among cowpea marketers in northern Nigeria, emphasizing the importance of family labor in sustaining market operations. Similarly, Ojo and Lawal (2020) observed that most grain traders in Kwara State belonged to households of between five and eight members, which they identified as optimal for maintaining business stability.

Table 3: Analysis of cost and return on cowpea marketing

Item	Average Cost (₦)	(%)
Fixed Costs Market rent	₦2,000	0.24
Storage facility	₦10,000	1.20
Equipment rental	₦1,000	0.12
Registration/levies	₦5,000	0.60
Business license	₦4,000	0.49
Total Fixed Cost (TFC)	₦22,000	2.63
Variable Costs (Purchase of cowpea (per bag))	₦800,000	9.57
Transportation per trip	₦2,000	0.24
Local handling/logistics	₦5,000	0.60
Packaging cost	₦1,200	0.14
Labor	₦2,500	0.30
Commission agent	₦500	0.06
Miscellaneous expenses	₦3,000	0.36
Total Variable Cost (TVC)	₦814,200	97.37
Total Cost (TC = TFC + TVC)	₦836,200	
Total Revenue (Sales of cowpea) Quantity (bags) X Price (Naira)	₦950,000 (10 X 95,000)	
Gross Margin (GM = TR – TVC)	₦135,800	
Net Return (NR = TR – TC)	₦113,800	
Return on Naira Spent (RNS = NR / TC)	0.14 (₦0.14)	

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Years of marketing experience of the Cowpea marketers

The results in Table 7 indicate that a majority of the respondents (35%) have between 6 and 10 years of marketing experience, while 26% have between 11 and 15 years of experience. About 23% have relatively short experience ranging from 1 to 5 years, 11% have been involved in the trade for 16 to 20 years, and only 5% have more than 20 years of experience. The mean marketing experience of approximately 10 years suggests that most cowpea marketers in the study area have a substantial period of practical exposure to the business.

These findings are consistent with those of Ojo et al. (2019), who reported that most cowpea traders in Kaduna State had between 7 and 12 years of marketing experience and that experience was significantly correlated with profit margin and efficiency. Similarly, Ibrahim and Adamu (2020) found an average of 9.8 years of marketing experience among cowpea traders in Kano State, noting that longer experience enhances market judgment and business sustainability. Lawal et al. (2021) also observed that years of marketing experience were positively related to sales performance and traders' ability to forecast price movements effectively.

Cooperative membership of the Cowpea marketers

The results in Table 8 show that 38 % of the respondents belong to one form of cooperative society or another, while the majority, representing 62 %, are not members of any cooperative organization. This indicates that less than half of the cowpea marketers in the study area participate in cooperative groups, suggesting limited engagement in collective marketing associations or trade-based organizations. This result is in line with the findings of Ibrahim et al. (2018), who observed that only 40 % of cowpea traders in Bauchi State belonged to cooperatives, attributing low participation to mistrust and poor cooperative management.

Factors Influencing Price Fluctuations in Cowpea Marketing

The regression results presented in Table 2 show that the model explaining price fluctuation in cowpea marketing is statistically significant, with an R value of 0.612 and an adjusted R square of 0.331. This means that approximately 33.1 % of the variation in price fluctuation among respondents is explained by the selected factors, while the remaining 66.9 % is attributable to other

variables not included in this analysis such as market intermediaries, foreign trade effects, and exchange rate variations. Seasonality and transportation have the highest and most significant positive effects on price fluctuation, with standardized coefficients (β) of 0.327 and 0.291 respectively. This indicates that fluctuations in seasonal supply and transport costs are the strongest determinants of cowpea price instability. Seasonal variation causes cyclical shortages and gluts that drive price swings, while high transportation costs amplify price differentials between producing and consuming areas. These findings agree with Ibrahim et al. (2019) and Muhammad and Adebayo (2020), who observed that production seasonality and transportation inefficiencies are key drivers of grain price volatility in northern Nigeria.

Storage conditions and market demand also significantly influence price fluctuation, with β values of 0.176 and 0.208 respectively, both statistically significant at the 5 % level. Poor storage facilities often compel traders to sell quickly during harvest periods when prices are low, while sudden surges in consumer demand increase prices. Similar outcomes were reported by Olayemi and Bello (2021), who found that inadequate storage and unpredictable demand patterns heightened market instability for legumes in Kano State.

Weather conditions, though moderate ($\beta = 0.151$, $p < 0.05$), have a significant positive effect, indicating that unpredictable rainfall and temperature patterns affect production volumes and consequently market prices. Government policy ($\beta = 0.132$, $p = 0.075$) and pest and disease incidence ($\beta = 0.116$, $p = 0.078$) have positive but weaker effects, implying that inconsistent policies and pest-related losses contribute to price changes, though their impacts are relatively indirect compared to seasonality and transportation. All the coefficients are positive, meaning that increases in any of the factors correspond to higher levels of price fluctuation. This result confirms that the cowpea market is highly sensitive to multiple interrelated shocks that affect both supply and demand. The results correspond with the conclusions of Tanko et al. (2021), who highlighted that infrastructural, climatic, and policy-related inefficiencies collectively undermine market stability for major grain crops in Nigeria.

Cost and Return

The analysis reveals that the total fixed cost incurred by cowpea marketers amounted to approximately ₦22,000, while variable costs accounted for ₦814,200. This confirms that cowpea marketing is predominantly variable-cost driven, with purchase and transportation expenses contributing the largest share. The total marketing cost was ₦836,200, and the total revenue realized stood at ₦950,000.

The gross margin of ₦135,800 suggests that after accounting for all variable expenses, traders still retain a

substantial operating surplus. The net return of ₦113,800 indicates that cowpea marketing is profitable in the study area. The return on naira spent (₦0.14) implies that for every ₦1 invested, a marketer earns ₦0.14 as profit, which reflects moderate marketing efficiency. This finding is consistent with similar studies by Musa et al. (2020) and Ibrahim and Audu (2018), who noted that cowpea marketing yields positive financial returns despite market and transport constraints. The results underscore the need for improved market infrastructure, reliable transportation systems, and accessible credit facilities to further enhance profitability and sustainability in cowpea marketing.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study found that seasonality, transportation costs, storage conditions, and market demand significantly influence cowpea price fluctuations in Sokoto Metropolis. Cowpea marketing is profitable despite existing challenges. Improving access to credit, market information, storage facilities, transportation infrastructure, cooperative activities, and marketing training will enhance efficiency and profitability.

REFERENCES

- Abdullahi, A., & Mohammed, M. (2020). Price fluctuations and seasonal dynamics in cowpea marketing in Northern Nigeria. *J. Agric. Econ. and Rural Develop.* 12(2), 45–56.
- Adamu, A., Ibrahim, M., & Bello, U. (2020). Climate characteristics and agricultural production systems in Sokoto State, Nigeria. *Nig. J. Agric. Res.* 15(1), 23–34.
- Adeoye, R. O., & Afolayan, A. (2019). Market conduct and pricing behavior among grain traders in Southwestern Nigeria. *J. Agric. Marketing and Policy Stud.* 6(2), 67–80.
- Audu, Y., & Aliyu, A. (2021). Dual occupation and income stability among grain marketers in Nigeria. *Nig. J. Agric. Econ.* 11(1), 55–68.
- Audu, Y., Lawal, A., & Musa, H. (2019). Gender participation in cowpea marketing in Adamawa State, Nigeria. *Nig. J. Agribusiness and Rural Develop.* 7(2), 88–99.
- Audu, Y., Lawal, A., & Musa, H. (2020). Educational attainment and marketing efficiency among grain traders in Benue State. *J. Agric. Extension and Rural Development*, 12(3), 120–131.
- Food and Agriculture Organization. (2022). FAOSTAT statistical database. FAO.
- Ibrahim, A., & Adamu, M. (2020). Marketing experience and business sustainability among cowpea traders in Kano State, Nigeria. *Nig. Agric. J.* 51(2), 90–102.
- Ibrahim, A., & Audu, Y. (2018). Marketing performance of cowpea traders in Northern Nigeria. *Nig. J. Agric. Econ.* 8(4), 132–146.
- Ibrahim, A., Bello, M., & Usman, S. (2019). Household size and marketing performance among cowpea traders in Northern Nigeria. *J. Rural Sociology and Agric. Develop.*, 10(1), 74–86.
- Lawal, A., Mohammed, U., & Bello, S. (2021). Marketing experience and sales performance among grain traders in Nigeria. *J. Agribusiness Manage.* 9(2), 101–114.
- Muhammad, A., & Adebayo, R. (2020). Transportation costs and grain price volatility in Northern Nigeria. *West African J. Agric. Econ.* 8(1), 45–59.
- National Population Commission. (2006). Population and housing census of the Federal Republic of Nigeria. NPC.
- Ogunleye, O. O., Adebayo, K. O., & Salawu, A. B. (2018). Profitability

- and constraints of cowpea marketing in Nigeria. *Nig. J. Agric. Econ.*, 9(1), 67–79.
- Ogunleye, O. O., Bello, A., & Adeyemi, T. (2020). Gender dynamics and access to credit among legume traders in Southwestern Nigeria. *J. Agribusiness and Rural Development*, 12(2), 84–95.
- Ojo, S., Bello, A., & Adamu, L. (2019). Demographic characteristics and efficiency of grain traders in Kaduna State. *J. Development Stud.*, 7(1), 78–90.
- Ojo, S., & Lawal, A. (2020). Household characteristics and business stability among grain traders in Kwara State. *Nig. J. Rural Development*, 14(2), 60–73.
- Olayemi, T., & Bello, A. (2021). Capital access and storage capacity as determinants of cowpea market performance in Kano State, Nigeria. *J. Agribusiness Management*, 9(1), 32–49.
- Olayemi, T., Bello, A., & Hassan, M. (2019). Occupational specialization and grain marketing in Southwestern Nigeria. *J. Agric. Marketing*, 8(3), 95–108.
- Tanko, M., Ahmed, I., & Jibrin, H. (2020). Socioeconomic characteristics and grain market participation in Niger State, Nigeria. *Nig. J. Soc. and Agric. Stud.* 8(2), 101–118.
- Tanko, M., Ahmed, I., & Jibrin, H. (2021). Infrastructural constraints and market stability of grain crops in Nigeria. *Nig. J. Agric. Policy and Development*, 10(1), 22–37.